

PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES FOR FORMING GENDER CULTURE IN PRIMARY GRADE STUDENTS

Egamberganova Makhbuba

Lecturer, Faculty of "Social Sciences and Humanities and Pedagogy", Urganch Innovation University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15093563>

Abstract. This article presents analytical information on the concept of gender culture, its formation, and methods in English lessons for primary school students.

Keywords: foreign language, gender culture, mutual respect, stereotypes, social adaptation, equal opportunities.

Аннотация. В данной статье представлены аналитические сведения о понятии гендерной культуры, ее формировании и методах на уроках английского языка для учащихся начальной школы.

Ключевые слова: иностранный язык, гендерная культура, взаимное уважение, стереотип, социальная адаптация, равные возможности.

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilari uchun ingliz tili darslarida gender madaniyati tushunchasi, uning shakllanishi va usullari haqida tahliliy ma'lumotlar keltirilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: chet tili, gender madaniyati, o'zaro hurmat, stereotip, ijtimoiy moslashuv, teng imkoniyatlar.

Today, the formation of gender culture is one of the most important directions of the education system. The inculcation of the principles of gender equality from a young age serves to ensure social justice and stability in society. Especially the development of gender culture in the primary school period has a positive impact on the future life of students.

Gender culture is a concept based on the equality of women and men in society, their equal rights and opportunities [1,12]. Gender equality is an important part of human rights, and the education system is considered a key factor in this direction [2]. The formation of gender culture, especially in primary schools, has a direct impact on the worldview of future generations.

Gender culture develops within the framework of the socio-normative system of society and is formed through pedagogical activity. The concept of gender equality means the equality of human rights, freedoms and opportunities regardless of gender.

Educational technologies play an important role in shaping gender culture. Therefore, it is necessary to use innovative technologies to eliminate gender stereotypes, ensure equal opportunities, and create a gender-inclusive environment.

Various pedagogical technologies can be used to form a gender culture. The most effective ones are considered below:

Interactive learning technologies

1. Explaining gender issues through role-playing and problem-based learning.
2. Building students' social interaction through group tasks.

Modular learning technology

1. Teaching gender-related topics in stages.
2. Conduct practical sessions on gender justice within each module.

Discussion and debate technologies

1. Organizing discussions on gender issues.
2. Developing students' critical thinking skills.

Information and Communication Technologies (ICT)

1. Use of electronic resources and visual materials.
2. Providing gender-related video, audio and multimedia products.

Life skills development technology

1. Research real-life situations related to gender equality.
2. Encourage students to observe the principles of equality in their daily lives.

The development of effective methods of teaching foreign languages is based on the results of the interaction of linguistics, psychology, pedagogy and related scientific fields. There is a lot of empirical data that emphasizes the need for in-depth study of factors affecting the modern science-educational and educational system. One of these factors is the gender factor. In modern linguistic research, the study of the role of each hemisphere in the implementation of speech activity, as well as the analysis of the features of their interaction in ensuring speech activity in mastering a foreign language, is becoming increasingly important. The theory of functional asymmetry of the brain, the features of lateralization and the relationship between the right and left hemispheres affect the development of language abilities and are determined by gender differences [3,11].

Pedagogical technologies are one of the effective tools for creating a gender culture, through which ideas of gender equality are conveyed to students. Some of these technologies are discussed below:

1. **Interactive learning technologies**– this method involves students being divided into groups and conducting various discussions on the topic of gender equality. This process allows students to freely express their thoughts and exchange ideas.

2. **Project method**– Students gain a deeper understanding of the topic by developing and implementing projects related to gender culture. For example, research projects on the topic "Gender Equality in My Family."

3. **Learning through play**– concepts of gender roles and equality are formed through the use of game methods, taking into account the age characteristics of primary school students.

4. **Information and communication technology (ICT)-based learning**– knowledge about gender culture is conveyed to students through electronic textbooks, interactive videos, and educational programs.

5. **Constructivist approach**– this method aims to develop students' independent thinking, critical thinking, and personal opinions on gender issues.

Studies on gender issues have shown that the formation of gender culture from an early age increases children's social adaptation and helps them understand the principles of equality in society in the future [4,13].

In conclusion, the process of forming a gender culture is an important stage for primary school students. The use of interactive and innovative pedagogical technologies in the education system makes a great contribution to the formation of students' awareness of gender equality. Therefore, teachers need to develop effective approaches to integrating gender issues into the educational process.

REFERENCES

1. Eagly, AH, & Wood, W. Social Role Theory of Sex Differences and Similarities. American Psychologist. 2012.
2. UNESCO. Gender Equality in Education. UNESCO Publishing.2017
3. *Christine Howe*.Gender and Classroom Interaction: A Research Review, Issue 138. Front Cover. SCRE, 1997 - Classroom environment - 56 pages.
4. T. G'afforova "Modern pedagogic text in Boshlang'ich educationthatUsing logs" "Tafakkur" - T. 2011.